

A Study of Burnout in Relation to Job Involvement of College Teachers in Himachal Pradesh

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Abstract

Teaching has been one of the oldest and most respected professions in the world. The task of teacher is shaping the future of citizens and thereby society and nation. Due to respectful duty, teacher has been respectful in all society through ancient to Buddhist period. In the modern period teacher is regarded as a custodian and architect of a nation. Today, there are many duties and responsibilities of a teachers working at different level of education. Burnout is the outcome of excessive stress. Many illnesses like liver and heart disease are likely due to psychological stresses of modern life. The percentage of burnout is likely higher today. Better understanding of this stress outcome has to be promoted. The study was delimited to the thirty four government and private degree Colleges located in territory of Himachal Pradesh and seven districts i.e. Hamirpur, Bilaspur, Una, Kangra, Shimla, Chamba and Mandi of Himachal Pradesh. The investigator in the present study has adopted descriptive survey method. The population for the present study comprised teachers teaching degree classes in government and private (aided and non-aided) colleges affiliated to Himachal Pradesh University. Since, it was not possible to cover all the colleges in the State of Himachal Pradesh, stratified random sampling technique was applied, first for selection of colleges by giving due weightage to type of management, mode of appointment, location and gender and secondly to draw the sample of 546 teachers from the colleges. In the present study, the researcher used the following tools for collection of data: Burnout Inventory (BI) developed by Karuna Shankar Misra (2005). Means, S.Ds. and t-value as well as analysis of variance (ANOVA) used as a statistical techniques to analyse and interpret the data.

Keywords: Burnout in Relation, Job Involvement, College Teachers.

Introduction

The job of a teacher is to teach the disciples to develop insight and reasoning that can be used to live a life. There is no doubt that profession of teaching is very large, deep and needs visionary actions. Teachers are often expected to correct social evils or problems while educating the students in academic and skill areas, providing enrichment activities, meeting the individual needs of students and encouraging student's moral and ethical development. Teachers have found their credibility eroding with large community.

The Maslach Burnout inventory was used by Worley et al. (2008) for studying the three factors namely emotional exhaustion, personal accomplishment and depersonalization of an individual. However, Mishra (2005) used non-accomplishment, depersonalization, emotional exhaustion, friction, task avoidance, distancing neglecting and easy going approach as the indicators of burnout among teachers. Depending on the particular case, burnout may be alleviated by changes in the work environment and job demands, as well as changes in the individual's behaviour and approach to work. If nothing changes, however, burnout tends to create a downward spiral, in which an unsustainable situation leads to exhaustion and dissatisfaction, which leads to poor performance, which in turn leads to a worsened work situation or even job loss and increased stress on the individual. In general terms, job involvement is the level at which an employee is engaged in his or her daily work. The level of job

involvement or engagement can be determined by a person's needs, values, work ethics (personal characteristics), the organizational setting (environment), and the characteristics of the job. According to Hafer & Martin (2006), employees with low job involvement can feel alienated by thinking that their job doesn't have a purpose, that they are not important in the organization, or they cannot see the connection between their work and who they believe themselves to be in 'life'. This definition implies that a person in job involvement sees his or her job 'as an important part of his/her self-concept' (Lawler & Hal, 1970). Researchers have shown that there is a relationship between job involvement, professional commitment and burnout. Job involvement is strongly related to many other theories of work motivation.

Objective of the study:

To study burnout in relation to job involvement of college teachers in Himachal Pradesh.

Hypothesis of the study:

There is no significant difference among different level of job involvement of college teachers in Himachal Pradesh on burn out.

Methodology of the study:

This chapter deals with description of method and procedure adopted to complete the present study. The plan and procedure is a blue print of a research study. Without planning, a researcher cannot achieve objectives with good reliability and validity. Therefore, method and procedure of any research is essential for quality information and thereby quality findings. The investigator in the present study has adopted descriptive survey method. The descriptive method involves quantitative information that can be tabulated along a continuum in numerical form. It involves gathering data that describe events and then organizes, tabulates, depicts, and describes the data collection (Glass & Hopkins, 1984). Descriptive research summarized many information in form of mean, median, mode, standard deviation, variance, percentage, correlation between variables etc. The descriptive research often uses quasi-experimental research design (Campbell & Stanley, 1963). Data collection in descriptive research includes surveys, interviews, observations, and portfolios. The descriptive research involves the description, recording, analysis and interpretation of conditions that exist. It involves some types of comparison or contrast and attempts to discover relationships between existing non-manipulated variables (Best, 1981).

POPULATION AND SAMPLE OF THE STUDY:

Population is the entire aggregation of cases or units that meet criteria set by investigator. According to Best (2007), "A population is any group of individuals who have one or more characteristics in common that are of interest to the researcher. The population for the present study comprised teachers teaching degree classes in government and private (aided and non-aided) colleges affiliated to Himachal Pradesh University. Since, it was not possible to cover all the colleges in the State of Himachal Pradesh, stratified random sampling technique was applied, first for selection of colleges by giving due weightage to type of management, mode of appointment, location and gender and secondly to draw the sample of 546 teachers from the colleges.

Tools and Techniques used: A researcher requires many data-gathering tools or techniques. Tools are essential for measurement of traits of variables and it they guide the researcher in data collection and also in evaluation. In the present study, the researcher used the following tools for collection of data: Burnout Inventory (BI) developed by Karuna Shankar Misra (2005).

Job Involvement Scale (JIS) developed by Santosh Dhar, Upinder Dhar & D.K. Srinastava (2001) is also used to collect the data.

The Burnout Inventory used in the present study was originally developed by Karuna Shankar Misra to measure burnout among teachers working in higher education. The BI contains 48 items and it measures burnout in terms of eight dimensions namely Emotional Exhaustion, Depersonalization and

Non-accomplishment, Friction, Task avoidance, Distancing, Neglecting and Easy going. Descriptive statistics like mean, S.D., skewness and kurtosis were calculated to see normality and other purposes. To find out difference between two groups t-test was used. To find out differences among different levels of job involvement on burnout of college teachers analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used.

Analysis and interpretation of the data:

After data collection and analysis of data, main work of researcher is to present results and interpretation in systematic and effective way.

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To find out differences among different levels of job involvement on burnout of college teachers, analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used. Mean and standard deviation of different level of job involvement on burnout of college teachers are given in Table-1. Summary of one way analysis of variance is given in Table 4.9. Means and standard deviations of college teachers with low, average and high job involvement on total burnout and its dimensions are presented in Figure 11 and Figure 12.

Figure-1: Showing means and S.Ds. of college teachers with low, average and high professional commitment on all dimensions of burnout

Figure 1 showing that on non-accomplishment, emotional exhaustion, friction, task avoidance, neglecting, and easygoing dimensions of burnout teachers with low job involvement is higher than average and high job involvement teachers. Mean of teachers with average job involvement is higher than high job involvement on these burnout dimensions. On depersonalization mean of teachers with average job involvement is higher than low and high job involvement teachers. But mean of teachers with low job involvement is higher than teachers with high job involvement on depersonalization. Means of teachers with low and average job involvement are similar but higher than teachers with high job involvement. Figure 2 shows that Mean of teachers with low and job involvement is higher than teachers with average and high job involvement on total burnout.

Figure-2: Showing means and S.Ds. of college teachers with low, average and high professional commitment on total burnout score

Table -1
Mean and standard deviation for college teachers with low, average and high job involvement on total burnout and its dimensions

	Lower			Average			High		
	N	Mean	S.D.	N	Mean	S.D.	N	Mean	S.D.
NA	115	14.835	4.965	218	14.257	5.990	213	12.300	5.266
Dp	115	14.391	5.100	218	15.349	5.745	213	13.352	5.050
EE	115	14.713	4.902	218	14.394	5.713	213	12.803	4.782
F	115	14.209	5.029	218	13.115	5.550	213	10.911	5.050
TA	115	15.035	4.559	218	13.830	5.426	213	11.986	4.870
D	115	14.278	4.905	218	14.427	5.531	213	12.207	5.293
N	115	14.557	5.023	218	13.674	5.908	213	12.310	5.551
EG	115	14.565	4.377	218	13.803	5.239	213	12.615	5.300
Total Burnout	115	116.583	32.196	218	112.849	39.145	213	98.484	36.026

Table-2
Summary of analysis of variance for difference among different level of job involvement on total burnout and its dimensions of college teachers

Variable	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Sum of Square	F	Probability
Non-Accomplishment	Between	628.985	2	314.493	10.366	.000*
	Within	16474.246	543	30.339		
	Total	17103.231	545	31.382		
Depersonalization	Between	429.518	2	214.759	7.507	.001*
	Within	15533.487	543	28.607		
	Total	15963.005	545	29.290		
	Between	383.815	2	191.908	7.104	.001*

Emotional Exhaustion	Within	14669.322	543	27.015		
	Total	15053.137	545	27.620		
Friction	Between	955.953	2	477.977	17.332	.000*
	Within	14974.429	543	27.577		
	Total	15930.383	545	29.230		
Task Avoidance	Between	772.932	2	386.466	15.223	.000*
	Within	13785.539	543	25.388		
	Total	14558.471	545	26.713		
Distancing	Between	612.699	2	306.349	10.857	.000*
	Within	15321.332	543	28.216		
	Total	15934.031	545	29.237		
Neglecting	Between	420.509	2	210.254	6.722	.001*
	Within	16983.808	543	31.278		
	Total	17404.317	545	31.935		
Easy Going	Between	317.289	2	158.644	6.112	.002*
	Within	14095.211	543	25.958		
	Total	14412.500	545	26.445		
Total Burnout Score	Between	32885.308	2	16442.654	12.301	.000*
	Within	725843.162	543	1336.728		
	Total	758728.471	545	1392.162		
*p<0.05(Significant at 0.05 level)						

Table-2 shows that obtained F-values for non-accomplishment, depersonalization, emotional exhaustion, friction, task avoidance, distancing, neglecting, easygoing and total burnout are 10.366, 7.507, 7.104, 17.332, 15.223, 10.857, 6.722, 6.112 and 12.301 respectively. Table 4.9 also shows that probability of F-values are much less than 0.05. This means that significant difference exists among teachers with low, average and high job involvement on total burnout and its dimensions.

Therefore, null hypothesis H_{06} , that "There is no significant difference among different level of job involvement of college teachers in Himachal Pradesh on burn out", is rejected.

Findings and Conclusion of the Study:

Significant differences were found among college teachers with low, average and high job involvement on non-accomplishment, depersonalization, emotional exhaustion, friction, task avoidance, distancing, neglecting and easy going dimensions of burnout and total burnout. So we can say that various seminars and workshops should be organized related to overcoming burnout and enhancing the job involvement of college teachers. Organizer should care that administrators and key persons in government should participate in seminars. College teachers should be given complete academic freedom to work efficiently and attain excellence. For this institution should provide proper facilities.

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